

MORAL GOVERNANCE AND SCHOOL HEADS PERFORMANCE IN SPECIAL GEOGRAPHIC AREA (SGA) OF BANGSAMORO REGION

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Moral Governance and School Heads Performance in Special Geographic Area (SGA) of Bangsamoro Region

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between moral governance practices and school heads' performance in the Special Geographic Area Division of the Bangsamoro Region. Using a descriptive-correlational design, the study assessed moral governance practices among 135 school heads from ten clusters, focusing on transparency, integrity, fairness, accountability, and corruption-free management. School heads' performance was evaluated across various domains, including instructional leadership, human resource management, and community involvement. Findings revealed high ratings for moral governance, with transparency being the strongest ($M = 4.98$). However, no significant relationship was found between moral governance and school heads' performance ($r = -0.026$, $p = 0.911$), suggesting moral governance has a minimal direct impact.

Keywords: *moral governance, school heads performance, special geographic area*

Introduction

In discussions on international development, governance has emerged as a central idea within the last fifteen years. The interests, requirements, and cultural background of the researchers influence the governance evaluations. Some take a more comprehensive approach, examining aspects of democracy and human rights in civil society, the business sector, the judiciary, and government institutions, while others concentrate primarily on corruption in the public sector.

The subject of good administration is nearly always divisive. There is debate and criticism surrounding the way governmental institutions handle public affairs and resources (Duque, 2014). The public is now able to expect greater standards of an ethical, transparent, and accountable public sector due to the spread of globalization, the exercise of democratization, and the explosion of new information and communication technology. In addition to supporting responsive public policy and high standards of performance in the public sector, these necessary principles of sustainable development and good governance are also essential in delaying the emergence of systemic corruption.

Transparency, integrity, and accountability are institutionalized in the Philippine government by the 1987 constitution. The most notable of these clauses is found in Article XI, Section 1 of the Constitution of 1987, which declares that "Public office is a public trust." Public servants and officers must constantly answer to the people, live modest lives, act with justice and patriotism, and serve them with the highest responsibility, integrity, loyalty, and efficiency.

In light of its duty to promote sound public administration and good governance, the MBHTE-BARMM upholds moral governance to protect DepEd's conduct in attaining the intended human service and development. In order to ensure proper conduct of DepEd officials from the Regional office down to the Schools and to promote efficient service delivery, which should translate to the educational growth of the society, the principles of governance are established in the rules and regulations. Thus, school administrators are required by governance to act in a way that promotes both societal advancement and the welfare of the Filipino people (Bem, 2014).

The whole management of the school, its success or failure, rests on the shoulders of the principal. The school's goals and objectives are determined by the principal, who also assigns responsibilities to staff members based on their areas of interest and expertise. Naturally, these goals and objectives must align with those of the country (Uyanga, 2008).

Though it is unclear exactly what is meant by "moral governance," the Bangsamoro leadership is committed to governing and leading the Moro people. Therefore, in relation to the work performance of school heads in Special Geographic Area Division in Bangsamoro region, the research will assess moral governance, which is defined by transparency, honesty, fairness, responsibility, and the lack of corruption.

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the relationship between moral governance practice and school heads performance among elementary and secondary school heads in Special Geographic Area Division in Bangsamoro Region. Specifically, this will answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of moral governance practice among Bangsamoro school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1. transparency;
 - 1.2. integrity;
 - 1.3. fairness, participation;
 - 1.4. accountability; and

- 1.5. absence of corruption?
2. To what extent of school heads' performance in terms of:
 - 2.1. instructional leadership;
 - 2.2. learning environment;
 - 2.3. parents' involvement and community partnership;
 - 2.4. human resource management and Development; and
 - 2.5. school leadership management and operations?
3. Is there a significant relationship between moral governance practice and school heads leadership performance?

Literature Review

Moral Governance

Moral governance, a fundamental concept in ethics and politics, underscores the importance of guiding principles, values, and ethical standards in a society or institution's decision-making and rule-setting processes. It posits that the actions and policies of governments, organizations, and leaders should be grounded in a strong ethical framework to promote justice, fairness, and the well-being of individuals and communities (Arjoon et al., 2018).

Moral governance is new in administration development in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao government and elsewhere. The expected moral governance to be adopted and implemented in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao shall be based on the teaching of the Prophet Muhammad (Peace Be Upon Him) when he organized the people of Makkah and Madinah. Prophet Muhammad (Peace Be Upon Him) categorically emphasized the importance of moral governance as morality and ethics as character-building (Susilawati et al., 2022).

The Bangsamoro Government is committed to practicing moral governance according to the distinct beliefs, cultures, and aspirations of its people (Adiong & Diampuan, 2021). It is committed to being responsible, service-oriented, and change-oriented for its people (BDACommunications, 2022). Moreover, the Bangsamoro shall act legally and legitimately, rationally, and delivatively in its policymaking and decision-making (Fernandez E., 2023).

Transparency

Transparency is designed to promote straightforward access to information, institutions, and processes (Risteska et al., 2010). Essentially, improved management techniques, resource use transparency, and stakeholder accountability can all lead to better educational provision (Abebe, 2012).

The concept of transparency has been divulged by Allah in the following Ayat: "O you who believe! When you deal with each other, in transactions involving future obligations in a fixed period of time, reduce them to writing. Let a scribe write-down faithfully as between the parties..." (Quran, Al-Baqarah, Beginning of the Ayat, 2:282). This verse states that every transaction must be written to avoid justice.

Applying the concept of transparency, corporation should also disclose information regarding its strategy, actions, contribution to the community and the use of resources and protection of environment (Haniffa, 2002)

Integrity

Everyone in society, especially the most marginalized, needs to believe that their welfare is entwined with that of the entire community. They have to think that everyone, even themselves, has equal access to opportunities. Nobody should feel left behind or alienated from society as a whole. The best way to communicate the worth of a governing body to society and its purpose is to give stakeholders the means to "maintain, enhance, or generally improve their well-being" (Zaman, 2020).

Integrity, defined as the consistency of actions, values, and principles, is a critical component of moral governance. According to Simons (2019), integrity ensures that leaders maintain transparency and adhere to ethical norms in decision-making. Public officials with integrity serve as role models, inspiring trust and promoting accountability within institutions.

In the context of the Philippines, the concept of "integrity" is closely tied to anti-corruption measures. Studies by Cruz and dela Torre (2021) highlight the importance of integrity in mitigating corruption, particularly in local government units. Their research found that leaders who prioritize integrity in governance create systems that minimize opportunities for graft and corruption.

Fairness

Fairness is promoted through equity principle. The rule of law where laws should be fair and enforced impartially to all (Risteska et al., 2010). Fairness points to equal treatment in fulfilling stakeholder rights based on the agreements and regulations. In daily interaction, for instance, school policies do not discriminate among schools' members at school (Sitepu, 2016).

Fair legal frameworks that are upheld by an unbiased or neutral regulatory body are necessary for good governance in order to fully protect the human rights of all stakeholders, with a focus on minorities' rights. A neutral, independent court and an impartial,

uncorruptible police force are both necessary for impartial enforcement (Zaman, 2020).

Participation

Participation is proved to improve the quality of education and the governance of educational institutions. A research demonstrates the positive relationship among participation, education quality and governance (Oxfam, 2017).

Absence of Corruption

The absence of corruption is not merely the lack of corrupt practices but also the presence of systems and mechanisms that prevent and address unethical behavior. According to Northouse (2021), moral governance cannot thrive without eradicating corruption, as it is the foundation for public trust and institutional credibility.

In a study conducted by Villanueva and Cruz (2020), the absence of corruption was shown to positively correlate with higher levels of public trust in local government units (LGUs). The research emphasized that communities with transparent governance and strict anti-corruption policies reported greater citizen satisfaction with public services.

Accountability

In the Holy Qur'an, the word *hesab* is repeated more than eight times in different verses (F, 1997) *Hesab* or 'account' is the root of accounting, and the references in the Holy Qur'an are to 'account' in its generic sense, relating to one's responsibility to 'account' to God on all matters relating to human effort for which every Muslim is 'accountable'.

The Muslims believe in the terms of accountability that they will be judged for whatever they do in this world in the hereafter (life after death). In Islam, It's the duty of each Muslim to fulfill the wills of Allah in order to seek his pleasure and the promised prizes in the life after death. Thus, it requires every action and word in this world must be in line with the Islamic teachings. It does not matter what action the Muslims do either *ibadah* (solah) or purchasing shares in the stock market, eating, sleeping like daily jobs they must follow the Islamic teaching framework carefully. The importance of accountability to the man's life also has been mentioned by Holy Quran: "...Lo the hearing and the sight and the heart – of each of these will be asked" (Quran, Bani Israill, 17:36)

Accountability is associated with participation, decentralization, empowerment, and transparency in management concepts. In order to meet the demands of efficiency and democracy, schools must implement some sort of accountability system wherein the political power of the leaders is exercised through three channels: monitoring, enforcement, and answerability (Maile, 2002). Depending on the organization and whether the decision is made internally or externally, there are differences in accountability (Risteska et al., 2010). But in order to maintain control and hold teachers accountable, principals need to keep an eye on things and provide information (Hanberger, 2016).

Responsibility

Responsibility refers to the organization's ability to control the running of rules or procedures (Larasati et al., 2018). The schools must make sure that the policy made is responded well by those in charge of. Tamayao (2014) explains that it is the informal actors like powerful families and organized crime syndicates whose influence impacts the local governments, in both rural and urban areas. Their influence, more often than not, translates into corruption through manipulation of government officials and the agencies of government, causing the distortion or else compromise of constructive, helpful, and legitimate government objectives while pursuing their own private, often illegal, interests. The literature on good governance presents some of the following elements or characteristics of the concept culled from the definitions given by multilateral institutions.

School Heads' Performance

The advancement of human cultures has resulted in a multitude of intricate issues for people living in the modern world. Management: It is believed that maintaining social life is a crucial component of leading social organizations that require certain controls and qualitative development.

According to Cunningham and Cordeiro (2006), the idea of a school administrator as someone who enforces regulations, manages a variety of duties, and maintains a daily agenda has evolved. They are now accountable for the students' academic achievement and the school's outcomes (Branch et al., 2013; Mitchell et al., 2015; Karada et al., 2015). Today, the school administrator is responsible for putting strategies into place to shape the school environment and get the educational institution ready for change (Hallinger & Heck, 2010; Park, 2019). Although the duties of a principal have become very important for both teachers and pupils, they are also difficult, demanding, stressful, and complex (Lindberg, 2012; Mahfouz, 2020; Oplatka, 2017). Effective school leadership development is now necessary due to the increasing demands and responsibilities placed on school principals (Huber, 2004; Ng & Szeto, 2016).

However, they are essential to maintaining control over schools and accomplishing their goals. However, it's important to understand how their personality traits link to their actions and how much the former influences the latter. Numerous studies have been done to examine the personalities of principals and how they make use of their natural skills. Furthermore, it is important to consider their captivating personality and lack of obvious controls over their actual academic performance.

Especially at a time of rapid global change, schools must transform into organizations that effectively provide strong teaching and deep learning. According to Elmore (2003), school reform is "a process, not an event," and "experts must manage this process" (p. 14). Moorosi & Bantwini, 2016; Yang, 2014). Thus, an organization's ability to fulfill its obligations and accomplish its goals is largely dependent on the performance of its principals. The more effectively principals carry out their responsibilities, the more the organization accomplishes its objectives.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design in an attempt to evaluate moral governance practices and the extent of performance among elementary and secondary school heads in the Special Geographic Area Division in the Bangsamoro Region.

Respondents

This study focused on ninety-eight (98) complete elementary schools and thirty-seven (37) secondary schools in the Special Geographic Area Division. The target population of this study comprised one hundred thirty-five (135) completely enumerated school heads, thus ensuring that all school heads were considered as respondents of the study.

Instrument

An adopted survey questionnaire titled "Good Governance and Management of Secondary Education Questionnaire" (GGMSEQ) was the instrument used for data collection on the moral governance practices among school head.

Results and Discussion

Moral Governance

The level of moral governance on the aspects of transparency, integrity, fairness, accountability, and the absence of corruption were included in the study.

Transparency

Table 1 shows the level of moral governance in terms of transparency. The weighted mean of 4.98 indicates a "Strongly Agree" interpretation, reflecting a highly favorable perception of moral governance in terms of transparency.

The high rating of transparency suggests that the school heads in the Special Geographic Area Division exhibit a strong commitment to open, honest, and accountable practices in their administrative functions. Transparency in governance ensures that all stakeholders are informed about decisions, actions, and financial dealings, fostering trust within the school system.

The concept of transparency has been divulged by Allah in the following Ayat: "O you who believe! When you deal with each other, in transactions involving future obligations in a fixed period of time, reduce them to writing. Let a scribe write-down faithfully as between the parties..." (Quran, Al-Baqarah, Beginning of the Ayat, 2:282). This verse states that every transaction must be written to avoid justice.

Table 1. *Level of Moral Governance in Terms of Transparency*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Providing accurate details about financing, academics, students and staff behavior so your administration efforts can be diverted to the most sensitive areas.	135	4.96	0.1896	Always Practice
2.	Providing a solid answer to such questions as where the majority of the budget is being directed to & what percentages of students are failing or passing each year.	135	4.98	0.1480	Always Practice
3.	Making information available and easily accessible by showing parents exactly what goes on in the school, so they are kept updated on all the relevant information about their child and can give relevant feedback.	135	4.99	0.1213	Always Practice
4.	Having aware of expenditure in order to prevent leakages in their financials.	135	4.99	0.1213	Always Practice
5.	Taking the initiative towards adopting a transparent system	135	4.99	0.0861	Always Practice
	Weighted Mean	135	4.98	0.0592	Always Practice

Integrity

Table 2 shows the level of moral governance in terms of integrity. The weighted mean of 4.95 reflects a "Strongly Agree" interpretation, indicating that the school administration is highly regarded for its integrity.

All groups and sectors of society, especially the most vulnerable, must feel that they have a stake in the entire society's well-being. They must believe that opportunities are equally available for everyone, themselves included. No one must feel excluded from mainstream society or be left behind. Enabling stakeholders "to maintain, enhance, or generally improve their well-being provides the most compelling message regarding (a governing body's) reason for existence and value to society" (Zaman, 2020).

Table 2. *Level Analysis of Moral Governance in Terms of Integrity*

Indicators		N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1.	Being honest and having strong moral principles.	135	4.90	0.2961	Strongly Agree
2.	Working during office hours.	135	4.96	0.1896	Strongly Agree
3.	Abiding rules, policies, and mandate of the Department of Education.	135	5.00	0.0000	Strongly Agree
4.	Treating the faculty and staff with respect and trust.	135	4.96	0.1896	Strongly Agree
5.	Being able to bear the consequences of the actions and take responsibility.	135	4.93	0.2629	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean		135	4.95	0.0863	Strongly Agree

Fairness

Table 3 displays the level of moral governance in terms of fairness. The weighted mean of 4.95 indicates a "Strongly Agree" interpretation, showing that the school head is highly perceived as fair in terms of moral governance.

Fair legal frameworks and impartial enforcement are critical elements of moral governance, as highlighted by Zaman (2020), who argues that effective governance requires an impartial and neutral regulatory body that protects the rights of all stakeholders, particularly minority groups. In the context of school leadership, fairness means that school heads are seen as making decisions that are just and equitable, ensuring the protection and consideration of the rights of both staff and students. This perception of fairness may enhance trust and cooperation among the school community, fostering a positive environment for learning and development. The high rating indicates that the school heads are perceived as embodying these principles, thus promoting a sense of justice and equality within their institutions.

Table 3. *Level of Moral Governance in Terms of Fairness*

Indicators		N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1.	Reaffirming that everyone will receive an equal opportunity for development and to be recognized.	135	4.95	0.2226	Strongly Agree
2.	Using clear, objective, predetermined criteria to make work decisions such as promotions, distributing project assignments and opportunities to attend conferences.	135	4.99	0.1213	Strongly Agree
3.	Having strong interpersonal relationship.	135	4.92	0.2746	Strongly Agree
4.	Being transparent about how decisions are made and the factors that are considered.	135	4.97	0.1702	Strongly Agree
5.	Cultivating an environment where people are comfortable sharing feedback.	135	4.93	0.2504	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean		135	4.95	0.0897	Strongly Agree

Accountability

Table 4 displays the level of moral governance in terms of accountability. The weighted mean of 4.95 indicates a "Strongly Agree" interpretation, demonstrating that the school head is perceived as highly accountable in their governance practices.

The Muslims believe in the terms of accountability that they will be judged for whatever they do in this world in the hereafter (life after death). In Islam, It's the duty of each Muslim to fulfill the wills of Allah in order to seek his pleasure and the promised prizes in the life after death. Thus, it requires every action and word in this world must be in line with the Islamic teachings. It does not matter what action the Muslims do either ibadah (solah) or purchasing shares in the stock market, eating , sleeping like daily jobs they must follow the Islamic teaching framework carefully. The importance of accountability to the man's life also has been mentioned by Holy Quran: "...Lo the hearing and the sight and the heart – of each of these will be asked" (Quran, Bani Israill, 17:36).

Table 4. *Level of Moral Governance in Terms of Accountability*

Indicators		N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1.	Establishment of clear and transparent rules for the appointment of educational managers bring about effective realization of educational goals.	135	4.96	0.2068	Strongly Agree
2.	Appropriate safeguarding of public fund and properties from abuse enhance effective educational system.	135	4.99	0.0861	Strongly Agree
3.	Allowing parents receive an annual report on the finance and academic performance of the school enhance quality learning.	135	4.96	0.2068	Strongly Agree
4.	Effective allocation of scarce resources in education enhance quality learning.	135	4.92	0.2746	Strongly Agree
5.	Effective record keeping and updated usually bring about quality education.	135	4.92	0.2746	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean		135	4.95	0.1196	Strongly Agree

Absence of Corruption

Table 5 shows the level of moral governance in terms of the absence of corruption, which has a weighted mean of 4.98, falling under the "Strongly Agree" category. This result indicates that the school community highly appreciates the efforts of the school head in maintaining an environment free from corruption. A high rating reflects commitment to ethical practice and openness in governance- suggesting that the actions of the school head in the above ways are very valuable to the stakeholders involved.

As argued by Rotberg (2009), institutions supporting good governance encompass not just great leadership, but also that of an independent, inquisitive, investigative press beyond what mere descriptive reporters provide. Strong and viable systems cannot solely suffice if an adequately conscious citizenry does not function or act at school level in being informed; in this scenario, awareness of consciousness on part of the community shall ensure it becomes a proper system of governance. The results highlight that the school community's commitment to fighting corruption is influenced not just by institutional efforts but by the collective values and actions of its members. The emphasis on absence of corruption indicates a strong governance culture that values transparency and accountability, which is essential in fostering trust and ethical practices within the school system.

Table 5. Level of Moral Governance in Terms of Absence of Corruption

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Establishment of clear and transparent rules for the appointment of educational managers bring about effective realization of educational goals.	135	4.96	0.2068	Strongly Agree
2.	Appropriate safeguarding of public fund and properties from abuse enhance effective educational system.	135	4.97	0.1702	Strongly Agree
3.	Allowing parents receive an annual report on the finance and academic performance of the school enhance quality learning.	135	4.99	0.1213	Strongly Agree
4.	Effective allocation of scarce resources in education enhance quality learning.	135	4.99	0.1213	Strongly Agree
5.	Effective record keeping and updated usually bring about quality education.	135	4.99	0.0861	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean		135	4.98	0.0631	Strongly Agree

School Head's Performance

The extent of school heads' performance on the aspect of instructional leadership, learning environment, parents' involvement and community partnership, human resource management and Development, and school leadership management and operations were measured in the study.

Instructional Leadership

Table 6 reveals that the school heads' performance in terms of instructional leadership is rated as "Very Satisfactory," with a weighted mean of 4.09. This indicates that school heads are highly effective in supporting teaching and learning within their schools. They provide technical assistance to teachers, implement programs aimed at improving academic performance, and promote the use of localized and contextualized materials to enhance learning. This level of performance suggests that the school heads are successfully fostering a positive educational environment that encourages both teacher development and student achievement.

The findings are consistent with the idea that a school head's personality characteristics, interests, and abilities can have a direct impact on their leadership performance. As noted by Gurr, D., Drysdale, L., & Mulford, B. (2005), principals' personality traits can positively influence the efficiency of students. Therefore, the school heads' ability to lead instructional initiatives effectively may be partly attributed to their personal attributes, which enable them to motivate and guide their staff in ways that directly improve student outcomes.

Table 6. School head's performance in terms of Instructional Leadership

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Teachers were observed and given technical assistance to improve their pedagogical/teaching competence.	4.12	Very Satisfactory
2.	Implemented the Kindergarten to grade 6 program with significant increase in the general scholastic average.	4.10	Very Satisfactory
3.	Initiated the production of localized and contextualized materials for kindergarten to grade 6.	3.98	Very Satisfactory
4.	Facilitated the implementation and contextualization of K to 12 curriculum that enhance teaching and learning under new normal situation.	3.94	Very Satisfactory
5.	Ensured alignment of curriculum instruction, resources and promoted varied assessment to measured learners performance.	4.34	Outstanding
Weighted Mean		4.09	Very Satisfactory

Scale: 4.21–5.00 – Outstanding | 3.41–4.20 – Very Satisfactory | 2.61–3.40 – Satisfactory | 1.81–2.60 – Unsatisfactory | 1.00–1.80 – Poor

Learning Environment

Table 7 reveals the school heads' performance in terms of learning environment. The weighted mean of 4.04 reflects that the school head's performance in creating a conducive learning environment is rated as "Very Satisfactory." This indicates a strong commitment to fostering a safe, child-friendly, and disaster-resilient school setting by implementing effective rules, maintaining facilities, and addressing disciplinary concerns promptly.

Peterson (1998) has conducted a research to study principals' performance and its aspects based on five different managerial, educational, human relationships, professional and administrative aspects presented by Weiss, K. then he studied and explained principals' personalities using Eysenck model in different aspects (introversion/extroversion) and neurotic (neuroticism/emotional stability) and at last he studied their relationship together. The importance and necessity of studying the relationship between principals'

personality characteristics and their performance in elementary, junior high and high schools come from the importance of educational management, their roles in pedagogical principles, their managerial, educational, human relationship, professional, administrative and personal differences in objectives realization.

Table 7. School head's performance in terms of Learning Environment

	Indicators	Mean	Description
1.	Provided safe ,child-friendly and bully -free environment for pupils by crafting the school rules and policies on discipline and by minimizing complaints and resolving disciplinary concerns on time.	4.06	Very Satisfactory
2.	Maintained disaster-free environment.	3.96	Very Satisfactory
3.	Ensured that buildings, academic and non-academic rooms, toilets and canteen are usable every month.	3.98	Very Satisfactory
4.	Formulated intervention program to determine the strength, weakness, opportunities, threats (SWOT) of the school.	4.10	Very Satisfactory
5.	Strengthen effective school Disaster Risk Reduction Management Plan (SDRRMP) to mitigate natural and man-made calamity including COVID 19 pandemic.	4.12	Very Satisfactory
Weighted Mean		4.04	Very Satisfactory

Scale: 4.21–5.00 – Outstanding | 3.41–4.20 – Very Satisfactory | 2.61–3.40 – Satisfactory | 1.81–2.60 – Unsatisfactory | 1.00–1.80 – Poor

Human Resource Management

Table 8 displays the school heads' performance in terms of human resource management. The weighted mean of 4.06 indicates that the school head's performance in human resource management is rated as "Very Satisfactory," demonstrating effective leadership in enhancing teacher and non-teaching staff competencies.

Any educational institution would only be successful if human resource management is done well since it has a direct bearing on the quality of teaching and school operations in general. For a social organization to meet its objectives, the manager of the organization--in this case, a school head--needs to possess specific characteristics, performance qualities, and responsibilities that contribute to the overall effectiveness of the organization," opine Moran and Garies (2004). From this study, results will indicate the following: characteristics among school heads of the Special Geographic Area Division in that school heads demonstrate their competency in showing excellent leadership while establishing a positive working environment in staff growth. These competencies lead to increased staff performance in their respective departments as well as enable them to realize their school's vision. Therefore, such findings consider the significance of strong leadership in human resource management that would ensure the success of schools.

Table 8. School head's performance in terms of Human Resource Management

	Indicators	Mean	Description
1.	Identified the RPMS core competencies of teachers, their 21st century skills and individual development for each teachers.	3.98	Very Satisfactory
2.	Encouraged all teachers to attend in any seminars/workshops and trainings within the rating period.	4.01	Very Satisfactory
3.	Encouraged teachers to enroll master's degree program within the rating period.	4.01	Very Satisfactory
4.	Provided technical assistance to teachers on matters pertaining to enhancement of classroom management, skills and instructional competence and to non-teaching personnel on support services within the RPMS cycle.	4.40	Outstanding
5.	Implement staff evaluation and development system (PPST Based-RPMS) to improve the performance of the school personnel.	4.02	Very Satisfactory
6.	Develop needs – based master plan, training design and resource package for identified priority needs teachers and non-teaching personnel.	4.12	Very Satisfactory
7.	Initiated and compiled teacher's professional documents in portfolios.	3.92	Very Satisfactory
Weighted Mean		4.06	Very Satisfactory

Scale: 4.21–5.00 – Outstanding | 3.41–4.20 – Very Satisfactory | 2.61–3.40 – Satisfactory | 1.81–2.60 – Unsatisfactory | 1.00–1.80 – Poor

Parents' Involvement and Community Partnership

Table 9 displays the school heads' performance in terms of parents' involvement and community partnership. The weighted mean of 3.96 indicates that the school head's performance in terms of parents' involvement and community partnership is rated as "Very Satisfactory," reflecting a strong commitment to fostering collaboration between the school and its stakeholders.

The discovery that school heads achieved a "Very Satisfactory" rating on the performance of parents' involvement and community partnership embodies their strength in strengthening school-community relationships. The excellent performance is an expression of the effort of the school heads in improving communication and cooperation with parents, a channel towards bettering student outcomes. According to Peterson (1998), school leaders play a critical role in managing relationships not only within the school but also in the broader community. This aligns with the research conducted by Weiss (1998), which identified key aspects of principals' performance, including their ability to foster human relationships and professional engagement. It therefore suggests that the aspects of the above elements are being used effectively by school heads to involve parents and community members in the education process, hence better

academic and social outcomes for students. This result strengthens the notion that community involvement and partnership is a key determinant of the success of school leadership.

Table 9. School head's performance in terms of Parents' Involvement and Community Partnership

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Ensured accomplished Homeroom PTA projects of the class advisers.	4.18	Very Satisfactory
2.	Acquired donations and resources from stakeholders for teachers and pupils' use.	4.10	Very Satisfactory
3.	Established stakeholders link to commit support the school programs.	3.98	Very Satisfactory
4.	Established school, family and community partnership to improve school facilities and performance in accordance with the requirements of new normal.	3.80	Very Satisfactory
5.	Created campus culture of shared governance facilitating the physical facilities development of the school that is shared and supported by the school community.	4.05	Very Satisfactory
6.	Enhanced the principle and practice of shared governance to support stewardship of learners learning outcome	3.96	Very Satisfactory
7.	Recognized accomplishments of stakeholders.	4.18	Very Satisfactory
8.	Mediated and ensured resolution of conflicts in school	3.79	Very Satisfactory
9.	Formulated school policies with stakeholders.	3.88	Very Satisfactory
10.	Harnessed participation of alumni and other organization (NGO's, LGU's, PPP).	3.73	Very Satisfactory
Weighted Mean		3.96	Very Satisfactory

Scale: 4.21–5.00 – Outstanding | 3.41–4.20 – Very Satisfactory | 2.61–3.40 – Satisfactory | 1.81–2.60 – Unsatisfactory | 1.00–1.80 – Poor

School Leadership and Management Operation

Table 10 shows the school heads' performance in terms of school leadership and management. The weighted mean of 4.15 indicates that the school head's performance in school leadership and management operations is rated as "Very Satisfactory," reflecting effective leadership in managing financial transparency, educational programs, and school improvement planning.

Weiss (1998) highlighted the importance of school leaders in achieving organizational success and fulfilling their responsibilities. This study's findings align with Weiss's assertion, as the school heads' high performance in leadership and management suggests they are effectively contributing to the overall success of their schools. Their ability to navigate complex leadership challenges and promote continuous improvement is vital to fostering an environment that supports both academic and operational excellence.

Table 10. School Leadership and Management Operation

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Utilized, liquidated and provided transparent financial reports.	4.45	Outstanding
2.	Improved SBM level of practice by performing school leadership, management and operations functions.	4.02	Very Satisfactory
3.	Led and implemented educational programs.	4.02	Very Satisfactory
4.	Applied principle of effective leadership and management in relation to school budgeting, personnel, resource utilization, financial management and technology use.	3.98	Very Satisfactory
5.	Requested and distributed instructional materials.	4.23	Outstanding
6.	Led the preparation of SIP/AIP and ensured participation of stakeholders.	4.25	Outstanding
Weighted Mean		4.15	Very Satisfactory

Scale: 4.21–5.00 – Outstanding | 3.41–4.20 – Very Satisfactory | 2.61–3.40 – Satisfactory | 1.81–2.60 – Unsatisfactory | 1.00–1.80 – Poor

Relationship Between Moral Governance Practice of the School Heads and their Performance

The table presents the results of a correlation analysis between Moral Governance and School Heads' Performance (OCPRF) using Kendall's Tau B, with corresponding p-values to determine statistical significance. The correlation analysis between Moral Governance and School Heads' Performance (OCPRF) reveals a very small negative correlation coefficient of -0.026, suggesting a negligible relationship between the two variables. With a p-value of 0.911, which is far above the 0.05 threshold, the result is not statistically significant, indicating that any observed relationship is likely due to chance. These findings imply that moral governance, as measured in this study, does not have a direct impact on school heads' performance.

Table 11. Correlation Analysis between Moral Governance and School Heads Performance (OCPRF)

		<i>Moral Governance</i>	<i>School Head Performance (OCPRF)</i>
Moral Governance	Kendall's Tau B	—	—
	p-value	—	—
School Head Performance (OCPRF)	Kendall's Tau B	-0.026	—
	p-value	0.911	—

The findings of the study suggest that moral governance practice, though critical, does not actually have a relationship with the school head's performance, at least in this context. The fact that the small negative correlation shows no statistical significance suggests that the performance of the school heads is being affected by other factors, as well. As Gurr, Drysdale, and Mulford (2005) point out, personality characteristics of school principals, such as their interests, abilities, and unique traits, can be of great influence in determining their performance. Personal characteristics, rather than governance practices, may have a greater impact on the

effectiveness of school leadership. It is also important that future studies investigate whether these personal factors and other contextual variables may play a role in school heads' performance. While moral governance is very important in ethical leadership, its influence on performance might be indirect or mediated by other factors not captured in this study.

Conclusions

The findings from this study reveal that the moral governance practices of school heads in the Bangsamoro region are highly valued by the school community, with components such as transparency, integrity, fairness, accountability, and the absence of corruption receiving "Strongly Agree" ratings. Transparency was rated the highest, with a weighted mean of 4.98, indicating the school heads' strong commitment to openness and ethical leadership. These practices reflect a leadership style rooted in Islamic principles of justice and equity, fostering a culture of trust and ethical governance within schools. Despite this, the study found no significant relationship between moral governance and school heads' performance (correlation coefficient of -0.026, $p = 0.911$), suggesting that moral governance alone does not directly influence their effectiveness.

Interestingly, school heads performed "Very Satisfactorily" in areas such as instructional leadership (mean: 4.09), learning environment (4.04), human resource management (4.06), and parents' involvement and community partnership (3.96), with "Outstanding" ratings for specific indicators like financial transparency and curriculum alignment. These findings suggest that factors other than moral governance, such as personal traits, external support, or contextual challenges, may have a greater impact on performance. To address this, it is recommended that school heads receive professional development focusing on instructional management, community engagement, and strategic leadership. By addressing these areas, school heads can enhance their effectiveness and bridge the gap between moral governance and performance, contributing to overall school improvement.

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